

MARK TWAIN AND HIS INFLUENCE ON UZBEK LITERATURE

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The analysis of the English literature is significant from practical point of view. Training students in the context of professional and specific aspects of the foreign languages, and also studying its genres helps them in the future to establish correct intercultural communication, to be well informed about linguistics and literature, obviously helps to improve literacy skills, to become among colleagues authoritative, stimulates professional growth in the professional environment.

Literature has always been a mirror of life; it reflects the social events, and offers pleasure to the readers. It's also known that the creative works of the ancestors and their literary heritage played an important role for the perfect development of every talented person. Learning creative experience of mentors, continuing their traditions gives the artist the opportunity of affecting the development of literature of his time.

In every period in the history of American literature a diversity of talented writers appears. Likewise, readers always exhibit a vast diversity of taste in what they want to read.

In the article one of the world's famous literal works of America written by Mark Twain have been discussed. Mark Twain left school at the age of twelve and went on to become one of American's best known and loved nationalistic authors. In spite of the shortness of his tenure, he reveals in his writings a unique insight into mid-nineteenth century "schooling." Most of his remarks and descriptions about education, people, and life in general, are satirical and humorous.

His novels, short stories and addresses reflect his society and cast shadows upon our own. Since education is an integral part of society, his views also reflect the educational ideas of the time.

Twain's writings are very involved with the concept of the child. His literature consists mainly of "boy-books" such as *Tan Sawyer* and *Huckleberry Finn*. He dwelt of his literary life in the wonderful time of childhood. His *Tom Sawyer* and *Huckleberry Finn* are studies of youth maturing through romantic exploits and finally being initiated into a society. His children are universal composites of all children, both past and present. They contain the qualities, mischievousness and shortcomings of all children.

Twain traveled frequently, kept voluminous journals about each trip, and eventually recorded his impressions in book form. He wrote kind and unkind things about each place he visited. He wrote on an international level so he has world fame.

The children in his books incorporate all the children he met with a few embellishments.

Twain’s books were often cynical and written in tongue-in-cheek style, so special care must be taken not to misinterpret or misrepresent his ideas. Twain also claimed to be a first-class liar and many of his stories are exaggerated tall tales. He seems to tell his most outrageous lies when he is trying to make his satire as biting as possible.

Twain’s books are written mainly about the little man in society or else they are autobiographical. Whichever way Twain chooses to write, his ideas and opinions are firmly reflected and elaborated upon. He sets himself up as an expert on almost everything, so of course he has an opinion on just about everything, usually biased. He writes with a "pen warmed up in hell".

We look at schooling in the mid-and-late nineteenth century America and see how the common school movement began and progressed. The teachers and their teaching methods are mentioned and commented on. Twain’s own view of nineteenth century schooling is studied to see how indicative it is of the times. His literal works focused on the satirical aspect of *Huck Finn* and threw more light on the author’s opinions about his times.

This work is devoted to the analysis of the world’s famous literal works of America written by Mark Twain and works of prominent Uzbek writer Said Akhmad. Both writers mostly wrote short stories and their similarities occur in the usage of satire in those works. Most of these writers’ remarks and descriptions, people, and life in general, are satirical and humorous.

Both writers’ novels, short stories and addresses reflect their society and cast shadows upon our own.

Said Akhmad wrote “Tog’ afsonasi”, “Zumrad”, “Muhabbatning tug’ilishi”, “Ko’zlarida o’t bor edi”, “Poyqadam”, “Alla”, “Iqbol chiroqlari”, he created true to life characters. His works are very popular with majestic usage of humor and ironical laugh at sneaking traditions which were interruption to the development of the country.

The main subjects of other translations of the 1920-1930's are in the same trend: proletarian literature (John Reed, Upton Sinclair), literature for children (Charles Major “Meeting with a bear”). As far as the number of translations is concerned, it must be said that novels written by Jack London were the most popular ones with translators. This tendency resulted from the general trend of Russian critics of the period under review to consider Jack London as one of the progressive writers, a true rebel and a symbol of opposition to the capitalist regime. Nevertheless, at the same time A. Startsev and S.Dinamov criticized such a narrow social approach to the work of the American writer. Even a cursory examination shows that Uzbek writers - translators of the first half of the 20th century gave more attention to the works of American writers as compared to the previous period.

The keen interest in Mark Twain`s works was still high and the search for the most appropriate translation of them into the Uzbek language was in progress as shown by translation of the "Tom Soyerning Sarguzashtlari" made by G.Gulam. In general, among the topics of literary works translated into Uzbek prevailed "criticizing capitalist world".

In general, the trends identified in the 1920-1930s remained unchanged in the next decades. Characteristically, in the 1940-50s the most famous of Mark Twain's novels such as "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer", "Huckleberry Finn", "A Connecticut Yankee in King Arthur's Court" were translated into the Uzbek language. The importance of these translations cannot be overemphasized since Uzbek readers had a good chance to become acquainted not only with separate translations of his works but to have the whole idea of creative work of the famous American writer, humorist and thinker.

Uzbek translations of the works of American writers revealing the theme of the World War II are presented by the novels written by Ernest Hemingway where the author wrote about the war in Spain.

Starting from the 1940s Uzbek writers-translators were deeply involved in translating American prose dealing with the problem of race discrimination. The classical novel "Uncle Tom's Cabin" written by Beecher Stowe, Mark Twain's novel "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn" and translations of the songs from Afro-American folklore allowed Uzbek readers to get the idea of the race conflict reflected in the American literature of the XIX-XX century, to understand a specific character of the Negro theme in the literature of the "white". At the same time, the novel "Uncle Tom's Cabin" by Beecher Stowe and "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn" by Mark Twain entered the list of books required for reading for Uzbek teenagers while "Tales of Uncle Remus", by Joel Chandler Harris was intended for the children under school age and allowed them to feel the peculiarity of the Negro folklore which was easily understood through the form of fairytales.

The matter of socio-cultural principles of selection of the works to be translated into the Uzbek language, as well as evaluation of the dynamics of perception of American literature in Uzbekistan during the twentieth century call for further investigation. The results of the research work on this problem can be used to make a holistic concept of functioning of the culture of another nation in multinational and intercultural space. They also can be applied in University education at the faculties of philology and culture in working out the courses dealing with national and regional components.

There are many Uzbek writers whose works contributed to the development of the Uzbek literature. We know that some philologists like Qodir Mirmuhammedov, Nizom Komilov are famous with their translated literary works. Some well-known

novelists also translated famous masterpieces of the world. (Cho’lpon, Mirzakalon Ismoilov, Mirtemir).

The great Uzbek poet and novelist G’afur G’ulom translated the world’s masterpieces either, but he is best loved by his Uzbek lyric poems, short stories and novels. G’afur G’ulom’s works appeared in the Uzbek Literature mid nineteenth century. In 1930 he translated into Uzbek the poem “Во весь голос” by Vladimir Mayakovskiy by the name “Хайқирик”. One may note the similarity between his novels and the great European novelists’ works. There is found the delicate similarity between his famous character “Shum bola” and Mark Twain’s “Tom Sawyer”. In my opinion, every reader can appreciate Uzbek version of “The adventures of Tom Sawyer” by G’afur G’ulom. The writer could transfer the scene, the spirit, and the images of the characters into Uzbek language professionally. Due to his contribution made to our literature “The adventures of Tom Sawyer” became beloved novel of every Uzbek reader. It shows that his works have great impact on the world’s literature.

In his works as “Tog’ afsonasi”, “Zumrad”, “Muhabbatning tug’ilishi”, “Ko’zlarida o’t bor edi”, “Poyqadam”, “Alla”, “Iqbol chiroqlari”, he created true to life characters. Like Mark Twain Said Akhmad’s main *weapon* in writing stories was satire. His works are very popular with majestic usage of humor and ironical laugh at sneaking traditions which were interruption to the development of the country. He laughs at such kind of people who are interference to the increase of modern life in the shape of stories like “Xanka and Tanka”, “Lampa shisha”.

Humor is main feature among the most important ingredients that make satire interesting, Twain’s style was predominantly humoristic story writing. He used to quarrel about the articles to publish with Orion who had no sense of humor. Eighteen year old Sam (Twain) told him:

“We need a little humor, things that make people laugh... We need to give a little life to The Journal.” Twain already had the sense of humor which he would develop first as a journalist, then as a lecturer and find attractive. According to Encyclopedia AMERICANA humor refers to “the comic or laughable... But humor is certainly multifaceted. It may be aggressive and derisive, ... it can be playful or intelligent, it can even be serious, as satire...; it cannot be false. Humor... cannot desert truth.”

The same with Said Akhmad, he was quick-witted and was able to compete with anyone about the usage of humor in literature. His master Abdulla Qahhor says about his works that they make feel the reader enjoyment, every line of his works can find way to the soul of reader. His usage of humor mostly seen in all works of him.

Being an American man Twain believed to independence in American way of life, he was against the slavery of white man but not black; he tried to criticize European countries life style and kept moving forward in his American way.

Mark Twain’s *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn* is to be classified among protest novels. Its main aim was to protest against some evil practices that were frequent in mid-19th century America frontier society. To make it more attractive to the readers and more effective to change society, Mark Twain used satire, which is a literary manner of denouncing, criticizing and laughing at the foibles, crimes or vices of a person or society, with the aim of correcting them. Usually, humor plays a great role and makes people laugh, which makes it easier for satire to reach its targets. “*Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*” is a book about Huck’s escapades as he helps Jim, a runaway slave, find freedom. Twain uses satire in this book to communicate his ideas about race, slavery, hypocrisy and the social climate. For example, toward the beginning of the book, Huck’s father imprisons and enslaves him. When Huck runs away and encounters Jim, who illegally escaped his enslavement, he initially feels conflicted about supporting Jim. This is satirical because in Huck’s society, it was against the law to enslave a white person, but not a black person. At the same time, it was legal for a white person to escape enslavement, but illegal for a black person to run away from a master.

Unlike situation can be seen in Said Akhmad’s position. He lived in the country which was under the colony of USSR and no mankind rights were acceptable there.

The writers who spoke the truth or wrote about sincere feelings of nation were accused, punished seriously. Though Said Akhmad was against old traditions or beliefs that prevented to nation’s development mentally and awakenment he was taken under pressure by soviet authority like many other writers of that period.

Said Akhmad was famous for his humor, which was done by him masterly and made the reader burst of laugh, because of his rich, wittily use of satire in his works. Said Akhmad wrote a lot of stories, those make today’s and yesterday’s readers soft feelings, generous senses, and heartfelt passion to life touch them upon. He used his “pen” progressively about taking into consideration every detail of human kind’s inner and outer world imaginations. Said Akhmad’s all short stories unlike other Uzbek writers’ works, are written in modern style of writing. He tried to draw picture of each story happenings philosophically universal; lyrical impressionability, colorful images were his great friends in writing. “Cho’l burguti”, ”O’rik domla”, “Lochin”, “Bo’ston”, “To’yboshi” works written by him are real modern Uzbek literature novelties of that time. The writer created his heroes with rich inner world coevals of his country.

In his works as “Tog afsonasi”, “Zumrad”, “Muhabbatning tug’ilishi”, “Ko’zlarinda o’t bor edi”, “Poyqadam”, “Alla”, “Iqbol chiroqlari”, he created true to life characters. Like Mark Twain Said Akhmad’s main *weapon* in writing stories was satire. His works are very popular with majestic usage of humor and ironical laugh at sneaking traditions, which were interruption to the development of the country. He

laughs at such kind of people who are interference to the increase of modern life in the shape of stories like “Xanka and Tanka”, “Lampa shisha”. Besides his short stories the writer published a great deal of interesting novels as “Ufq”, “Qadr don dalalar”, “Hukm”, “Jimjitlik”, and as dramaturgic writer he wrote “Kelinlar qo’zg’oloni”, “Kuyov” and other works. In his works as “Tog’ afsonasi”, “Zumrad”, “Muhabbatning tug’ilishi”, “Ko’zlaringda o’t bor edi”, “Poyqadam”, “Alla”, “Iqbol chiroqlari”, he created true to life characters. Like Mark Twain Said Akhmads main *weapon* in writing stories was satire. His works are very popular with majestic usage of humor and ironical laugh at sneaking traditions which were interruption to the development of the country. He laughs at such kind of people who are interference to the increase of modern life in the shape of stories like “Xanka and Tanka”, “Lampa shisha”. Besides his short stories the writer published a great deal of interesting novels as “Ufq”, “Qadr don dalalar”, “Hukm”, “Jimjitlik”, and as dramaturgic writer he wrote “Kelinlar qo’zg’oloni”, “Kuyov” and other works.

Cognitive characteristics and learning theory reveal that adults would like to compare the language features, the similarities and differences of different languages so that they can master them better on a higher level besides employing memory, repetition and imitation when they are learning a new foreign language.

The contrast between English and Uzbek, as a branch of contrast linguistics, has a bright application prospect on which base the contrast between English and Uzbek can be used to help students master the foreign language more conveniently and more efficiently. Therefore, the contrastive study between English and Uzbek should be further explored deeply and systematically.

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